

Assessment of Mobile-Phone-Integration on Teacher Training Programs among Colleges of Education Pre-service Teachers in North-West, Nigeria

Haruna, Umar¹

Email: Ufarouq253@gmail.com

Phone: 08060908285,08110343878

Awolusi, Bayo Ezekiel¹

Email: awolusib@gmail.com

Phone: 08081097410, 09066028842

¹Department of Computer Science Education, Federal University of Education, Zaria

Abstract:

There is a saying that “No Nation rises above the quality of its Teachers”. This study investigates ‘Mobile-Phone-Integration on Teacher Training Programs among Colleges of Education Pre-service Teachers in North-West, Nigeria’. The population of the study is 2,629 consisting of all NCE II Computer Science Pre-service teachers during the 2023/2024 academic session in colleges of education in Northwest, Nigeria, sample of 335 is determined using Crejcie and Morgan (1970). Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The study adapted a questionnaire titled: “Smartphone Utilization for Academic Purposes (MUAP)”. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used for data analysis. The study revealed a high level of Mobile Phone utilization for academic purposes among pre-service teachers. However, the study also revealed considerable challenges hindering effective Mobile-Phone utilization, including affordability among others. The findings underscore the need for policy interventions to enhance on affordability of Mobile-devices, thereby fostering an environment conducive to Mobile Phone-based learning. This research contributes to the discourse on innovation in teacher education, highlighting the potential of Mobile-Phones to foster 21st-century teaching practices in Nigerian tertiary education. This is in line with the findings of Becker et al., (2017) that Innovations in technology are influencing how students’ access, learn, retain, and apply information. The study concluded that, the level of Mobile-Phone utilization among pre-service teachers in the colleges is very high as well as the challenges. The study therefore, recommended among others that: Affordable Mobile-Phones should be provided.

Keywords: Curriculum Integration, Mobile Phone utilization, teacher education, Digital Divide.

Introduction

The essence of using technology is for education, communication, social interaction, commercial, as well as playing important role in terms of development of individuals and group of people in the world (Hatch, 2018). The rapid adaptation of young generation to the technological developments increases aim for using Mobile Phone device in different aspects of their life. Mobile Phone has now become an immediate *friend* and the best tool for social and commercial benefits to the youth in the 21st Century (Scott, 2015). The number of individuals using the mobile devices is three times more than the computer users (Baptista & Oliveira, 2015). These computers abolish time and place concept whereas the mobile phones are also more popular and sometimes efficient (Ricci, Rokach, & Shapira, 2015).

Mobile Phone as a general-purpose mobile device has impact on so many aspects of human endeavor. Its mobility, affordability and easy access made the youth to easily integrate it into their daily activities. It is observed that Mobile Phone play important roles even in education, academic research, planning and development. The use of conventional methods of teaching and dominating all the class activities, doing the talking and chalking with little or no student’s participation is now boring to both students and lecturers, especially in the teacher training institutions (Elbaz, 2018). This approach is seriously discouraged by most researches because, it leads to poor concentration, boredom, unattractiveness, difficulty in assessment of individual differences as a result of large class size (over population) and so on. Learning requires some certain facilities in order to take place especially for students in tertiary institutions of learning like the polytechnics, colleges of education and universities. Those required facilities simplifies teaching and learning processes (academic activities) from both teachers and student’s sides, these instruments are sometimes called teaching and learning materials or instructional aides. These set of facilities differs depending on the time and place of use also on subject or topic to be thought, as most of the facilities are designed to achieve a specific purpose. Traditionally, instructional aides are improvised using some of the available resources that can be easily obtained at a given period of time, to teach a particular course or topic; in mathematics, students are taught

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topics like shapes using cardboard paper or any thick plain paper, each piece of the card is cut to represent a shape like triangle, square, rectangle, circle and so on. Improvisation of such materials requires an adequate knowledge of shapes and skills of shaping and molding simple objectives to a simple and reasonable object or compound and reasonable object for use in classrooms to deliver a lecture on something or explain a concept or phenomena. The use of instructional aid makes teaching and learning easier than just the use of a verbal or written word to explain a phenomena or concept. In order to achieve above, makes the adoption of technologies in place ranging from simple technology to the complex, from natural substances to artificial substances in order to achieve a determined goal.

In the 20th and 21st century, it is expected that modern technology should dominate almost every aspect of human endeavor, the use of digital technology that deals with personal computers (internet and intranet, desktops, laptops, notebooks, iPad, light pen, electronic ink and electronic papers, projectors, Interactive white boards and so on) (Elbaz, 2018). The 21st century students are not limited to the knowledge of life, even in the classroom settings, where there are now various forms of technology (Harding, 2016). The face of the contemporary classroom is ever-changing (Gargiulo & Metcalf, 2017). Innovations in technology are influencing how students' access, learn, retain, and apply information, and it influences pedagogy of educators using presentation softwares and modules using technology as instructional aid and training media (Becker et al., 2017). Since technology is the application of scientific knowledge to the practical aims of human life; classroom technology to achieve educational task may include computer applications, smart boards, digital projectors and other technological devices. Such devices capture students' attention; however, educators must stay up-to-date on technology trends in the world and how to integrate it into their pedagogy (Selwyn, 2016). Despite the possession of various technologies for use in education, it is observed that none of the technologies clearly supports collaborative learning and give students equal right to sources of information and at the same time provides a means of sharing the information within themselves, having access to the source of all forms of information; such as, text, audio, audio-visual and video to easily access, manipulate, utilize and share with one another, that would help students to equally store and retrieve all information anywhere and anytime as well as assist the students to have a high level of retention.

Objectives of the Study

This research intends to achieve the following objectives; to:

1. examine the level of Mobile Phone utilization for academic purposes among pre-service teachers in Federal Colleges of Education in North-West Nigeria.
2. find out the challenges associated to Mobile Phone utilization for academic purposes among pre-service teachers in Federal Colleges of Education in North-West Nigeria.

Research Questions

The study raised the following questions to guide the study:

1. What is the level of Mobile Phone utilization for academic purposes among pre-service teachers in Federal Colleges of Education in North-West Nigeria?
2. What are the challenges associated to Mobile Phone utilization for academic purposes among pre-service teachers in Federal Colleges of Education in North-West Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

1. H_{01} : There is no significant difference between utilization of Mobile-Phone and academic achievement among colleges of Education pre-service teachers in North-West, Nigeria.
2. H_{02} : There is no significant difference between challenges associated with utilization of Mobile-Phone and academic achievement among colleges of Education pre-service teachers in North-West, Nigeria

Methodology

Descriptive survey design was adopted for this study, the justification for using survey research design was that, the study samples some pre-service teachers in 5 colleges of education to find the level of their Mobile Phone utilization for academic purposes, and examine the challenges. The population of the study is 2,629 consisting of all NCE II Computer Science Pre-service teachers during the 2023/2024 academic session in colleges of education in Northwest, Nigeria, from which a sample of 335 was determined as recommended by Crejcie and Morgan (1970) when total population is 2629. A sample being a subset of the population chosen to participate in a study was 335.

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The researcher used questionnaire titled: Mobile Phone Utilization for Academic Purposes (MUAP) for data collection. The MUAP instrument has three sections. Section “A” captured respondents’ biodata, section “B” data on the level of Mobile Phone utilization among pre-service teachers under study, “C” elicited data on the challenges of Mobile Phone utilization for academic purposes among pre-service teachers. The instrument was validated by experts in Measurement and Evaluation from Faculty of Education Ahmadu Bello University (ABU), Zaria. The Cronbach reliability was used to test the reliability of the test items. The reliability of the 30 items of the instrument was 0.947. The instrument questionnaire items were found to be reliable. This was in confirmation of test of reliability by Spiegel, (1992) Stevens, (1986), and Olayiwola, (2010). According to them an instrument is considered reliable if it lies between 0 and 1, and that the closer the calculated reliability coefficient is to zero, the less reliable is the instrument, and the closer the calculated reliability co-efficient is to 1, the more reliable is the instrument. This therefore confirms the reliability of the data collection instrument used as fit for the main work. The questionnaires were administered to the respondents in their various lecture rooms. The questionnaires were filled by the students immediately and returned before the end of their classes. The period of data administration and collection took three weeks with the help of two research assistants.

Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) IBM version 26.0 was used in the analysis of the data collected. Frequency counts and percentage was used for the bio data variables. The research questions were answered using item frequency of the four Likert scale options and their mean and standard deviations for each item in each of the ten items of the table. The cumulative mean is compared with a standard mean of 2.500. The null hypotheses were tested with Chi square statistical tool to assess the significance of each of the three cumulative variables of the instrument. The chi square is used because the data is ordinal and to determine it’s significance Chi square is the more appropriate statistical method to put in place. All the null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance.

Presentation of Results

Answering Research Questions

Table 1 (Question One): What is the level of Mobile Phone utilization for academic purposes among pre-service teachers in FCEs in North wester Nigeria ?

S/ No	ITEMS	HU	U	NU	HNU	MEAN	STD	DECISION
1	I use my Mobile Phone to search for multimedia documents on Google	99	112	50	48	2.848	0.981	Agree
2	My Mobile Phone enables me to access books from E-libraries	112	108	39	50	2.913	0.612	Agree
3	I make use of Mobile Phone to search for meaning of words in the dictionary/thesaurus.	110	97	48	54	2.851	0.823	Agree
4	I use my Mobile Phone to view and note articles, citations from the Google Scholar.	100	108	64	37	2.877	0.881	Agree
5	I also use my Mobile Phone to collect soft copy of lecture materials (notes) from lecturers	99	117	51	42	2.883	1.024	Agree
6	My Mobile Phone enables me to access life educational programs prepared by other institutions.	98	80	77	54	2.718	1.041	Agree
7	I use my Mobile Phone to record voice lectures from the lessons in the class for revision sake	96	104	64	45	2.812	1.044	Agree
8	I also use my Mobile Phone to record videos during practical classes for future replay to improve my retention ability.	103	101	63	42	2.858	0.814	Agree

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9	My Mobile Phone helps me in accessing Academic Calendar of the session and other vital relevant information from the College.	96	108	67	38		0.723	Agree
						2.848		
10	I use my Mobile Phone to access relevant educational videos from You-tube and other video blogs for academic purpose..	98	112	57	42		0.800	Agree
						2.865		
	CUMULATIVE MEAN					2.847		Agree

Decision Mean = 2.500 (HU=Highly Utilized, U=Utilized, NU=Not Utilized, HNU=Highly Not Utilized)

Table 1 shows the responses of preservice teachers on the level of smart phone utilization for academic purposes in Federal College of Education in Northwest Nigeria. Item one of the table says: I use my smart phone to search for multimedia documents on google, the responses shows that 99 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones for educational purposes, 112 are utilizing while 50 are not utilizing and 48 are highly not utilizing their smart phone to search for multimedia documents on google. The second item says: My Mobile phone enables me to access books from E-libraries, the responses shows that 112 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones for educational purposes, 108 are utilizing while 39 are not utilizing and 50 are highly not utilizing their Mobile phone to enable them access books from E-libraries. The third item says: the responses shows that 110 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones for searching for meaning of words in the dictionary/thesaurus, 97 are utilizing while 48 are not utilizing and 54 are highly not utilizing their Mobile phone in searching for meaning of words in the dictionary/thesaurus. The fourth item says: the responses shows that 100 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones to view note articles, citations from the Google Scholar, 108 are utilizing while 64 are not utilizing and 37 are highly not utilizing their Mobile phone to view note articles, citations from the Google Scholar. The fifth item says: the responses shows that 99 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones to collect soft copy of lecture materials (notes) from lecturers, 117 are utilizing while 51 are not utilizing and 42 are highly not utilizing their Mobile phone to collect soft copy of lecture materials (notes) from lecturers.

The sixth item says: the responses shows that 98 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones to access life educational programs prepared by other institutions, 80 are utilizing while 77 are not utilizing and 54 are highly not utilizing their Mobile phone to enables them access life educational programs prepared by other institutions. The seventh item says: the responses shows that 96 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones to record voice lectures from the lessons in the class for revision sake, 104 are utilizing while 64 are not utilizing and 45 are highly not utilizing their Mobile phone to record voice lectures from the lessons in the class for revision sake. The eighth item says: the responses shows that 103 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones to record videos during practical classes for future replay to improve my retention ability, 101 are utilizing while 63 are not utilizing and 42 are highly not utilizing their Mobile phone to record videos during practical classes for future replay to improve my retention ability. The ninth item says: the responses shows that 96 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones to accessing Academic Calendar of the session and other vital relevant information from the College, 108 are utilizing while 67 are not utilizing and 38 are highly not utilizing their Mobile phone in accessing Academic Calendar of the session and other vital relevant information from the College. The tenth item says: the responses shows that 98 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones to access relevant educational videos from You-tube and other video blogs for academic purpose, 112 are utilizing while 57 are not utilizing and 42 are highly not utilizing their Mobile phone to access relevant educational videos from You-tube and other video blogs for academic purpose.

Table 2 (Question Two): What are the challenges that affect the effective use of Mobile Phone?

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	MEAN	STD	DECISION
1	Cost of purchasing Mobile Phone with all functionality is high	110	103	46	50	2.883	1.041	Agree
2	Network issue is a challenge, as failure from network providers affects the efficiency of the system	101	109	60	39	2.880	1.045	Agree

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3	Implementing Mobile Phone into teacher requires some rules and regulations/blueprint	102	98	60	49	2.819	0.817	Agree
4	Cost of data to access the network is another challenge	101	102	70	36	2.867	0.881	Agree
5	Variation in size, speed and storage capacity of the Mobile Phone is also a challenge as some may have lower than the required capacity for some applications	89	114	57	49	2.786	1.044	Agree
6	Perception of stakeholders towards the integration of Mobile Phone utilization in academic purposes varies	107	104	50	48	2.874	1.046	Agree
7	Readiness from the government, curriculum planners, schools, parents and students etc is another challenge	90	106	64	49	2.767	1.044	Agree
8	Difficulty in handling the class when each student operates individually with his Mobile Phone	89	90	70	60	2.673	0.814	Agree
9	Battery lifespan is another challenge as not all phones can last for long without draining charge.	90	89	75	55	2.693	0.714	Agree
10	Non physical engagements in some activities especially that has to do with laboratory practicals and the likes.	92	89	70	58	2.696	0.811	Agree
CUMULATIVE MEAN						2.793		Agree

Decision Mean = 2.500 (SA=Strongly Agreed, A=Agreed, NA=Not Agreed, SNA=Strongly Not Agreed)

Table 2 shows the responses of pre-service teachers on level of challenges of Mobile phone utilization for academic purposes in Federal College of Education in Northwest Nigeria. Item one in the table says: Cost of purchasing Mobile phone with all functionality is high, the responses shows that 110 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones for educational purposes, 103 are utilizing while 46 are not utilizing and 50 are highly not utilizing, Cost of purchasing Mobile phone with all functionality is high. Item two in the table says: Cost of purchasing Mobile phone with all functionality is high, the responses shows that 101 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones for educational purposes, 109 are utilizing while 60 are not utilizing and 39 are highly not utilizing, Network issue is a challenge, as failure from network providers affects the efficiency of the system. Item three in the table says: Implementing Mobile phone into teacher requires some rules and regulations/blueprint, the responses shows that 102 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones for educational purposes, 98 are utilizing while 60 are not utilizing and 49 are highly not utilizing, Implementing Mobile phone into teacher requires some rules and regulations/blueprint.

Item four in the table says: Cost of data to access the network is another challenge, the responses shows that 101 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones for educational purposes, 102 are utilizing while 70 are not utilizing and 36 are highly not utilizing, Cost of data to access the network is another challenge. Item fifth in the table says: Variation in size, speed and storage capacity of the Mobile phone is also a challenge as some may have lower than the required capacity for some applications, the responses shows that 89 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones for educational purposes, 114 are utilizing while 57 are not utilizing and 49 are highly not utilizing, Variation in size, speed and storage capacity of the Mobile phone is also a challenge as some may have lower than the required capacity for some applications. Item sixth in the table says: Perception of stakeholders towards the integration of Mobile phone utilization in academic purposes varies, the responses shows that 107 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones for educational purposes, 104 are utilizing while 50 are not utilizing and 48 are highly not utilizing, Perception of stakeholders towards the integration of Mobile phone utilization in academic purposes varies.

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Item seventh in the table says: Difficulty in handling the class when each student operates individually with his Mobile phone, the responses shows that 90 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones for educational purposes, 106 are utilizing while 64 are not utilizing and 49 are highly not utilizing, Readiness from the government, curriculum planners, schools, parents and students etc. is another challenge. Item eighth in the table says: Readiness from the government, curriculum planners, schools, parents and students etc. is another challenge, the responses shows that 89 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones for educational purposes, 90 are utilizing while 70 are not utilizing and 60 are highly not utilizing, Battery lifespan is another challenge as not all phones can last for long without draining charge. Item ninth in the table says: Readiness from the government, curriculum planners, schools, parents and students etc. is another challenge, the responses shows that 90 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones for educational purposes, 89 are utilizing while 75 are not utilizing and 55 are highly not utilizing, Battery lifespan is another challenge as not all phones can last for long without draining charge. Item tenth in the table says: Non-physical engagements in some activities especially that has to do with laboratory practical and the likes. etc. is another challenge, the responses shows that 92 of the respondents are highly utilizing their smart phones for educational purposes, 89 are utilizing while 70 are not utilizing and 58 are highly not utilizing, Non-physical engagements in some activities especially that has to do with laboratory practical and the likes.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference between utilization of Mobile-Phone and academic achievement among colleges of Education pre-service teachers in North-West, Nigeria.

Table 3: Chi square (X^2)—statistics on significance of the level of Mobile Phone utilization for academic purposes among pre-service teachers in FCE in North-west Nigeria.

Variable	SA	A	D	SD	Total	Df	X^2 computed	X^2 critical	P-Value
Level of Mobile Phone utilization for academic purposes	114	93	52	50	309	6	47.481	40.113	0.006
	104.3	98.1	62.6	44.0					

p calculated = 0.006 < 0.05, x^2 computed = 47 > X^2 critical value of 40.113 at df 6 (SA=Strongly Agreed, A=Agreed, NA=Not Agreed, SNA=Strongly Not Agreed)

Results of the Chi square (X^2) statistics in table 3 shows that the level of Mobile Phone utilization for academic purposes among pre-service teachers in FCE in North-west Nigeria, is significant. Reason being that the chi square (X^2) statistics showed that the calculated p value of 0.006 is lower than the 0.05 alpha level of significance and its calculated Chi square (X^2) value of 47.481 is above the chi square (X^2) critical value of 40.113 at df 27. The observed counts are 114, 93, 52 and 50 for Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree and Strongly Disagreed respectively.

This outcome showed that the level of Mobile Phone utilization for academic purposes among pre-service teachers in FCEs in North-west Nigeria, is very significant. Therefore the null hypothesis which state, there is no significant difference between utilization of Mobile-Phone and academic achievement among colleges of Education pre-service teachers in North-West, Nigeria, is hereby rejected.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference between challenges associated with utilization of Mobile Phone and academic achievement among colleges of Education pre-service teachers in North-West, Nigeria..

Table 4: Chi square (X^2)—statistics on significance of the challenges affecting the effective utilization of Mobile Phone for academic purposes among pre-service teachers in FCE in North-west Nigeria,.

Variable	SA	A	D	SD	Total	Df	X^2 computed	X^2 critical	P-Value
Challenges affecting	110	103	46	50	309	6	58.907	40.113	0.017

utilization of Mobile Phone for academic purposes	97.1	100.4	62.2	49.3
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p calculated = 0.017 < 0.05, χ^2 computed = 58.907 > χ^2 critical value of 40.113 at df 6

Results of the Chi square (χ^2) statistics in table 4 shows that challenges affecting the effective utilization of Mobile Phone for academic purposes among pre-service teachers in FCE in North-west Nigeria, is significant.

Reason being that the chi square (χ^2) statistics showed that the calculated p value of 0.017 is lower than the 0.05 alpha level of significance and its calculated Chi square (χ^2) value of 58.907 is above the chi square (χ^2) critical value of 40.113 at df 27. The observed counts are 110, 103, 46 and 50 for strongly agree, Agree, Disagree and strongly disagreed respectively.

This outcome showed that the challenges affecting the effective utilization of Mobile Phone for academic purposes among pre-service teachers in FCE in North-west Nigeria, is very significant. Therefore the null hypothesis which state that, there is no significant difference between challenges associated with utilization of Mobile Phone and academic achievement among colleges of Education pre-service teachers in North-West, Nigeria, is hereby rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The level of Mobile phone utilization for academic purposes among pre-service teachers in FCE in North-west Nigeria is very high and commendable this is because the cumulative mean response agreement level of 2.847 is higher than the decision mean of 2.500. Specifically, most Majority opined that My Mobile phone enables me to access books from E-libraries as this view had the highest mean agreement level of 2.913 with details showing that while 112 strongly agree, 108 agreed, as against 39 disagreed and the rest 50 strongly disagreed. Also, majority of pre-service teachers use their Mobile phone to collect soft copy of lecture materials (notes) from lecturers, as this has the second highest mean response of 2.883 as a total of 99 strongly agreed while 117 agreed as against 51 that disagreed and the rest 42 strongly disagreed. In summary, the level of Mobile phone utilization for academic purposes among pre-service teachers in FCE in North-west Nigeria is very high and commendable especially as majority use their phones to access books from E-libraries and use their Mobile phones to collect soft copy of lecture materials (notes) from lecturers among others.

The challenges that affect the effective use of Mobile phones, are very great and enormous as the cumulative mean agreement level of 2.793 is higher than the 2.500 decision mean. Specifically, the highest challenge is that Cost of purchasing Mobile phone with all functionality is high as this attracted the highest mean agreement level of 2.883 as details showed that 110 strongly agreed, 103 agreed, as against 46 that disagreed and the rest 50 strongly disagreed. In the same vein another very serious challenge is Network issue is a challenge, as failure from network providers affects the efficiency of the system as this attracted the second highest mean of 2.880 as 101 strongly agreed, while 109 agreed as against 60 disagreed and 39 strongly disagreed. In summary, the challenges that affect the effective use of Mobile phones, are very great and enormous as the cumulative mean agreement level of 2.793 is higher than the 2.500 decision mean, especially as Cost of purchasing Mobile phone with all functionality and Network issue is a challenge.

Conclusion

It is therefore concluded that: The level of Mobile Phone utilization for academic purposes among pre-service teachers in FCEs in North-west Nigeria is very high and commendable especially as majority use their Mobile Phone to access books from E-libraries and use their Mobile Phone to collect soft copy of lecture materials (notes) from lecturers and even use them prepare for the exams. The challenges that affect the effective use of Mobile Phone, are very great and enormous as the cumulative mean agreement level of 2.793 is higher than the 2.500 decision mean, especially as Cost of purchasing Mobile Phone with all functionality and Network issue is very high.

Recommendations

1. Integrate digital literacy training into the training to enhance pre-services' skills in utilizing Mobile phones for academic purposes which will promote the development and utilization of Open Education Resources (OER) to reduce reliance and costly materials and develop policies supporting Mobile learning, ensuring equitable access to educational resources and addressing digital divide concerns, also provide ongoing supports and training for teacher educators to effectively integrate Mobile technology into their teaching practices.

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2. The Federal Government and educational institutions should consider subsidizing Mobile devices with essential functionalities for pre-service teachers in Federal Colleges of Education (FCEs) in Nigeria through collaborative partnerships with Mobile technology companies and Educational technology companies to provide affordable mobile devices, data plans and educational resources to reduce reliance on costly materials and invest in improving telecommunication infrastructure to address network challenges, ensuring reliable internet access in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria. Also conduct regular needs assessment to identify specific challenges with the network and develop target interventions.

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